

**Peer Support in Community Mental Health:
A Narrative Review Aligned with Ireland's HSE
and Clinical Psychology Practice**

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Abstract

This narrative review explores the integration of Peer Support Workers (PSWs) within community mental health services in Ireland, with a focus on alignment with Health Service Executive (HSE) policies and clinical psychology practice. Drawing on contemporary literature and Irish policy frameworks such as *Sharing the Vision* and the *National Framework for Recovery in Mental Health*, the review examines the theoretical foundations, implementation challenges, and policy developments that shape peer support in the Irish context. Key themes include the value of lived experience, recovery-oriented care, supervision needs, training inconsistencies, and organisational culture change. The review proposes actionable recommendations for enhancing PSW integration, including standardised training, protected supervision time, evaluation systems, and cultural transformation. The findings support a paradigm shift towards more inclusive, person-centred mental health care that values experiential knowledge alongside clinical expertise.

Keywords: Peer Support Workers, community mental health, recovery-oriented care, Health Service Executive (HSE), lived experience, clinical psychology, supervision, Irish mental health policy

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Introduction

According to Mutschler et al. (2021), peer support in community mental health services represents a progressive step towards recovery-oriented care, aligning with current policy directions. Repper and Carter (2011) define peer support workers (PSWs) as people who have lived through mental health challenges and offer support. They bring experiential knowledge into the clinical environment. According to the Department of Health (2020), the primary support of PSWs is through empathy, hope-driven, and mutuality in therapeutic relationships, as well as person-centred support to service users. However, Zisman-Ilami and Byrne (2022) note that integrating lived experience within formal care structures can challenge traditional hierarchical models by positioning experiential insight alongside professional expertise.

In Ireland, the Health Service Executive (HSE) identified peer support as one of the recovery-based services across the Community Healthcare Organisations (CHOs), supported by mental health policy, which shares the vision implemented in 2020, as outlined on HSE.ie (2016). Collaboration between peer support and psychologists is expected to increase in multidisciplinary teams, and practices should be revised to add co-production and involvement of service users. O'Dwyer O'Brien (2022) explored the role of peer support workers and their integration into the Irish mental health system, which remains under-researched and unevenly implemented.

This narrative review aims to critically explore the evidence associated with peer support models in community-based care and analyse their alignment with the Irish HSE policies and framework. It seeks to connect the lived experience and professional expertise in the mental health sector.

Theoretical Background and Context

Research conducted by Shalaby and Agyapong (2020) states that peer support aligns with the overarching recovery movement that has emerged to bridge the gap between psychiatric treatment and biomedical needs. The recovery module is based on inclusion, unconditional support for mental health recovery and at the same time challenging traditional clinical compliance and diagnosis.

As presented by Byrom (2018), the recovery process is more personal, focusing on framing understanding in terms of values, feelings, and changing attitudes, all within the context of grounded hope and self-determination. In this context, PSWs are representing the providers who have themselves experienced mental health difficulties. This understanding, gained through experience, acknowledges and forms the different basis of the therapeutic alliance, which can foster great trust, empathy, and authenticity in service to the users. However, this may contrast with clinical roles, which are constrained by the professional regulations and medicalised understanding of mental illness.

According to the theory outlined by Kolb (1984), experiential learning provides a psychological understanding of the value of peer support based on the presented mode through direct experience, reflection, conceptualisation, and experimentation. PSWs operate from a place of lived experience, providing the possibility of creating resilience and forming a

recovery model that best suits the user. The existence of PSWs is making expertise favourable not just to users, but also to professionals.

Structured peer support may have benefits, and the integration of PSW in the mental health system presents a complex understanding. On the other hand, Naslund et al. (2016) note that tension may arise when experiential roles confront institutional protocols, particularly in the clinical risk professional hierarchy, and confidentiality. Peer support effectiveness is well-connected in a context-dependent manner, and this is influenced by various factors, such as the organisation's culture, role clarity, and the level of training and supervision provided.

As presented by Norton et al. (2023), peer support is considered an emerging practice in the Irish context. Even so, associated bodies and the HSE have started to structure the roles of PSWs, and in CHOs, implementation varies. For a clinical psychologist, it is vital to understand the theoretical foundation, and they must work with traditional specific models while also adapting to new ways of thinking and creating inclusive, person-centred care settings.

Policy Alignment with the HSE

The Health Service Executive has increased the alignment between its mental health services and recovery-oriented care, placing a value on community-based care and person-centred care over the past decade. One of the key strategies identified is the use of PSWs across formal inclusion, according to the Department of Health (2020), based on the same source, which is more clearly highlighted in *Sharing the Vision: A Mental Health Policy for Everyone (HSE, 2020)*, that presents a roadmap for services modernisation. The policy promotes the employment and integration of people with disabilities (PWs) across the CHO, recognising their roles in enhancing user engagement and accommodating therapeutic relationships grounded in mutuality. The policy, "Sharing the Vision," has been updated from its previous format, "A Vision for Change," and introduces the concept of recovery-based services in Ireland. The difference between the 2006 policy, which was presented as a conceptual groundwork, and the updated format of 2020 is that the latter has more visibly concrete commitments, focusing on co-production, trauma-informed care, and the design of lived experiences introduced in the services.

Other documents that provide guidance are the National Framework for Mental Health (HSE, 2018), which states that the service does not direct recovery; it is a personal journey. This framework requires mental health professionals, including clinical psychologists, to engage in roles as collaborators, mentors, and advocates for recovery, rather than being sole authorities. At the same time, it introduces national recovery indicators, organisational standards, and guidelines relevant to peer support integration. By introducing these policies, they are providing a clear supervision structure, encouraging CHOs to create specific PSW roles within multidisciplinary teams, and ensuring appropriate training through accredited courses. The inclusion of PSWs in the field to work alongside clinical psychologists, occupational therapists, nurses, and other healthcare professionals presents a balance of responsibility and power, as well as a more democratic model for the mental health care sector.

Even so, the policies that are implemented vary across Ireland. As stated by Hunt and Byrne (2019), a percentage of CHOs have recognised peer support more than others, resulting in an inconsistency in recruitment, training, and integration practices. Moreover, the lack of protected supervision time can disturbance between collaboration between PSWs and clinical staff.

Even if the policy environment in Ireland is increasingly supportive of peer-informed care models, it has created a dual responsibility: to uphold the evidence-based standard of care and to advocate for the inclusion of service user voices. The *National Framework for Recovery in Mental Health* (HSE, 2018). By introducing psychological practice into the HSE guideline, it means engaging with peer support not as a separate entity, but as part of the component of ethical, person-centred service delivery.

In conclusion, the Irish mental health policies strongly support the integration of peer support with community settings. These policies provide a clear rationale for change and an invitation for clinical psychologists to reconsider their roles in collaboration with those who can share their lived experiences within the mental health care system.

Challenges and Considerations for Implementation

Despite the favourable direction of Ireland's policy frameworks, the application of peer support in mental health community care still faces several practical and systemic challenges. One of the most significant issues is the lack of role clarity, as PSWs do not clearly specify the boundaries between clinical and non-clinical responsibilities (Hunt & Byrne, 2019). Without clear duty clarification in their roles, PSWs may experience role confusion, which can lead to inefficiencies and tension within other teams.

Inconsistent training standard is another critical concern. Even if some CHOs offer structured coursework and accreditation programs, others lack a coherent framework for preparing PSWs for the complexities of the mental health environment (HSE, 2020). Additionally, for their professional growth, peer support is critical, particularly in clinical and peer-led supervision structures. However, many services fail to support it, resulting in burnout and high turnover among peer staff, as stated by O'Dwyer O'Brien (2022) in their research.

Another challenge is the cultural barrier within healthcare settings. Experiential knowledge can be misinterpreted and undervalued by the traditional biomedical models. This dynamic can compromise the legitimacy of PSWs and create friction within hierarchical structures (Zisman-Ilani & Byrne, 2022). Limited funding and staffing shortages are among the most common issues in rural or under-resourced Community Health Organisations (CHOs), making it even more challenging to integrate peer support in these roles. Services may struggle to justify the addition of peer workers when the service is already stretched, even if service user satisfaction has increased and hospitalisation has been reduced due to the long-term benefits of the peer support intervention (Repper & Carter, 2011).

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed for a better integration of peer support within the community mental health service in Ireland:

1. Standardise Training and Accreditation

The HSE should establish a nationally recognised training program for PSWs. It should also include core competencies, trauma-informed care principles, and clear role boundaries. The establishment of accredited training programs is essential to standardising peer support practice, enhancing role legitimacy, and facilitating effective collaboration within multidisciplinary teams. As Hunt and Byrne (2019) highlight, the absence of standardised training contributes to professional tensions and a lack of integration. Nationally endorsed training can help establish clear expectations and promote confidence among professionals. Ensure that PSWs are adequately prepared for their roles and responsibilities.

2. Introduce Protected Supervision Time

The implementation of protected supervision time for Peer Support Workers is essential to support their professional development and emotional resilience. This supervision should include reflective spaces that are peer-led and structural clinical oversight, which is adjusted to the unique position of PSWs within the multidisciplinary team. According to Mental Health Reform (2019), the absence of this kind of framework frequently leads to emotional exhaustion and high turnover. Supervision acts as a buffer against the emotional toll of peer work. It supports PSW in managing boundaries, dealing with trauma triggers and navigating their dual identity as service users and professionals.

3. Create Evaluation and Monitoring System

A national monitoring and evaluation system should be developed to assess the impact, outcomes, and fidelity of peer support interventions across the system. It should include qualitative and quantitative metrics to capture service user feedback, staff perceptions, and organisational outcomes, such as reduced hospitalisation rates, improved therapeutic alliance, and further enhancement of recovery markers. These tools should be designed in cooperation with peer workers, service users, and clinical teams to ensure their relevance and accuracy. HSE (2019) noted that monitoring the outcome is essential in creating a focus on recovery approaches to mainstream services.

4. Promote Organisational Culture Change

Introducing peer support inside a community of mental health requires a cultural shift across all levels of the organisation. Resistance often comes not from policy gaps but from clinical hierarchies, existing stigma around lived experience, and risk-averse attitudes in traditional psychiatric care (Zisman-Ilani & Byrne, 2022). Taking this into consideration, cultural change initiatives must involve all staff in reflective training that challenges stereotypes and fosters an environment of appreciation for experiential knowledge. These initiatives should promote co-production, shared decision-making, and recovery-oriented language, aiming to normalise the participation of peer supporters as equal team members.

Conclusion

The involvement of peer support is a revolutionary opportunity within Irish mental health system, offering lived experience, values-driven, recovery-oriented in comparison with the traditional clinical approach. This narrative review has highlighted that the integration of Peer Support Workers into Community Healthcare Organisations is in alignment with national policies such as "Sharing the Vision" and the "National Framework for Recovery in Mental Health" where the implementation of lived experience in care delivery is highly recommended, not as a secondary but as a vital component of holistic mental health service.

However, there are still persistent challenges, including inconsistent training and differences in implementation across CHOs. Maintaining good functionality and understanding of peer support requires coordinated actions at multiple levels in the health system, from national policies to local practice. Creating opportunities for peer support work in multidisciplinary teams, providing structured training and clear supervision frameworks, and support from clinical staff will ensure that service users receive a first-class service.

This shift requires an understanding and co-production from clinical psychologists and future practitioners, as well as respect for lived experiences and commitment to reshape therapeutic relationships in line with recovery values, by supporting the role of PSWs, and given the credible evidence that well-implemented programs can make the Irish mental health system a genuinely person-centred and inclusive system.

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